

Quality of life among the students of Gujranwala Medical College, Gujranwala

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Abstract:

Background and Definition: Quality of life is defined as one's subjective perception of one's own well-being, within one's socio-cultural context or as the satisfaction of desires and pleasures and the accomplishments of the ideal of perception [1]

MATERIALS AND METHODS: A cross-sectional study design was conducted at GUJRANWALA MEDICAL COLLEGE, GUJRANWALA. A total of 100 students were chosen through Random Sampling in which 20 students belonged to each class .A Quality of life-based questionnaire was used, and analysis was done.

RESULTS: There were just 1% students who think that they have a very poor quality of life, 57% think that they have a good quality of life and 29% have a very good quality of life. 12% are of the view that their quality of life is neither good nor poor

Conclusion: This study demonstrates that majority of the medical students have a good Quality of life. A small number of them have a very good Quality of life, while a negligible number of them have a poor or very poor quality of life .Students are especially more satisfied with their physical health when compared with other domains .Majority of them rarely have feelings of anxiety ,depression, and despair

Key Words; Gujranwala , Quality Of Life ,Medical Students,

INTRODUCTION:

Life as a doctor or medical student causes particular challenges and stressors that have an impact on Quality of life .Quality of life is the general well-being of individuals and societies .It is a product of interplay among social health ,physical and psychological development during their academic session. A systemic analysis was conducted to take an overview of a medical student's Quality of life.Mental problems such as stress ,anxiety ,depression and impaired cognitive ability have been described among medical students and are associated with their academic and professionals performance.It encompasses the assessment and control of those environmental factors impacting their behavior that can potentially affect the Quality of life.

It also refers to the ability of a student to adapt comfortably to different social situations and act appropriately in a variety of settings during academic life.An article regarding this topic was reviewed that compares the quality of life among medical students and a reference population, this research work concludes with the fact that medical students have been experiencing lower levels of Quality of life when compared with the general population. [2] In another study, medical students gave significantly higher scores for their quality of life than to their medical school related quality of life [3] The aim of this study is to assess Quality of life of medical students and to explore the influencing factors of quality of life.

Materials and Methods:

A quantitative survey was conducted at Gujranwala Medical College, Gujranwala. The technique used was the Cross-sectional study. A total of 100 students were chosen through Random Sampling in which 20 students belonged each class, and their age was in the range of 19 to 24 years old. All the students who were willing to answer the questions and who studied in the GMC were included in the study group. Those students who were not willing to answer and those who have diagnosed some mental illness or serious disease or disability were excluded from the research group. A QOL based questionnaire was used, and the performance was distributed among the students generally, and precise guidance was given to the students to fill in the performance. Questions were composed in easily understandable, simple words. Questions were described precisely and correctly relevant to the theme of the research work, moreover, in order to make it less time consuming it was made in the tabulated manner in which options were provided against each question.

After collecting the performance, frequency table of each question was made n data was analyzed.

Results:-

We distributed 100 questionnaires among students all of them were filled in by students. The demographic profiles well as QOL rating of these students are as follows:

QOL rating: students perception about their quality of life.

	Classes				
	1 st year	2 nd year	3 rd year	4 th year	5 th year
Male	5	5	5	5	5
Female	15	15	15	15	15
Hosteller	18	19	17	19	16
Day scholar	2	1	3	1	4
Quality of life among students of above classes					
Very poor	1	0	0	0	0
Poor	0	1	0	0	0
Neither poor nor good	4	2	2	0	4
Good	10	14	7	15	11
Very good	5	3	11	5	5

From a total 100 students, 20 students were chosen from each of five classes, i.e., 1st yr ,2nd yr ,3rd yr ,4th yr and ,5th yr. Out of total of 20 students from each class 5 were males, and 15 were females out of these 20 from 1st yr 18 were hostilities 2 were day scholars, from second yr 19 were hostelling and 1 was day scholar, from 3rd yr 17 were hostelling 3 were day scholars ,from 4 the yr 19 were hostilities 1 was day scholar and from 5th yr 16 were hostilities and 4 were day scholars.

QUALITY OF LIFE of medical students was analyzed on the basis of four domains, i.e.,

1. PHYSICAL DOMAIN
2. PSYCHOLOGICAL DOMAIN
3. SOCIAL DOMAIN
4. ENVIRONMENTAL DOMAIN

A number of questions were added in each domain .Only those questions which were representative of that domain were analyzed. Which are as follows?

Physical domain	Statements	Dissatisfied	neutral	Satisfied
	How much are you satisfied with your health?	16	17	67
	How satisfied are you with sleep?	18	15	67
	How satisfied are you with your ability to perform?	14	17	69
	How satisfied are you with your capacity to work?	13	10	77
Social domain	How satisfied are you with your personal relationships?	5	18	77
	How satisfied are you with your condition of living?	6	21	73
	How satisfied are you with your support from your friends?	6	10	84
Psychological domain		Never	seldom	Often

Psychological domain		Never	seldom	Often
	How often do you have negative feelings like mood changes anxiety depression and despair?	44	35	21
		Little	Moderate	Extreme
	How much do you feel your stress have been increased?	40	42	18
	How much do you feel that academic load is greater than your capacity?	40	41	19
Environmental domain		Little	Moderate	Extreme
	How healthy is your physical environment ?	28	49	23
	To what extent do you have an opportunity for leisure activity?	16	34	50
	How well are you able to get around?	15	98	37

Discussion:

A number of other questions were also asked in the questionnaire to get an estimate of Quality of life of the students.

PHYSICAL DOMAIN:

How much are you satisfied with your health?

How much are you satisfied with your sleep?

How satisfied are you with your ability to perform?

How satisfied are you with your capacity for work?

How much do u enjoy your life?

How much do u have enough energy for everyday life?

Are you able to accept your bodily appearance?

How much do you feel that u have abandoned your daily exercise routine?

How much do you feel the need for recreational places around your college area?

How much do you feel that fruits and a healthy diet are readily available in a hostel?"

PSYCHOLOGICAL DOMAIN:

How well are you able to concentrate?

How often do you have negative feelings like mood changes, anxiety ,depression ,despair ?

How much do you feel your stress has been increased?

How much do you feel that academic load is greater than your capacity ?

How safe you feel in your daily life?

To what extent do you feel your life meaningful?

How much do you fear future?

How much do you feel that you find sufficient time for relaxation?

How much do you feel that your behavior has been changed towards your family members?

How much do you feel that your daily sleep-wake cycle is disturbed?

How much do you feel that you are jealous of your friend's success?

How much do you feel inferior to others?

SOCIAL DOMAIN:

How much do you feel that you have sacrificed family events for professionals?

How much are satisfied with your personal relationship?

How much are satisfied with your living condition?

How much are satisfied with your support from your friends?

To what extent you think you feel accepted by people you know?

ENVIRONMENTAL DOMAIN:

How healthy is your physical environment?

To what extent do you have an opportunity for leisure activity?

How well are u able to get around?

In PHYSICAL DOMAIN results obtained after analysis of 100 questionnaire shows that 10 % of the students were of the view that they are dissatisfied with their physical health ,67% of the students were satisfied ,18 % of the students felt that they are dissatisfied with their sleeping habits and 67% felt that they are satisfied, 14 % of the students were dissatisfied with their ability to perform while 69 % were satisfied, 13% of the students were dissatisfied with their capacity to work while 77 % were satisfied.

As far as SOCIAL DOMAIN is concerned 5% of students are of views that are dissatisfied with their personal relationship. And 77 % are satisfied, 6% are dissatisfied with the condition of living, 73% are satisfied, 21% being neutral, 6% of students are dissatisfied with their support from friends, but 84% are satisfied, so the overall majority of students enjoy the good social life.

As far as psychological domain is concerned, students were asked about negative feelings like mood changes like anxiety depression despair, 44% of them are of the view that they never had such feelings, 35% of these had these feelings seldom, and 24% often are disturbed by such feelings. 40% students have a view that after entering the medical profession there has been a little increase in stress, 42% feel a moderate increase, 18% feel that there is extreme stress. 40% of students feel that they have more load than their capacity to work and 41% feel that there is a moderate increase in academic load, 19% feel an extreme increase in academic load with respect to their capacity.

When we consider the environment of medical students some questions were asked like, how healthy is their physical environment, 28% were of the view that physical environment is a little healthy, 49% feel that environment is moderately healthy, 23% feel that their environment is extremely healthy. 16% of medical students feel that they have little opportunity for leisure activity, 34% feel that they have a moderate opportunity for leisure activity, 50% feel that they have significant opportunity. 15% of medical students feel that they have little opportunity to get around, 48% feel that they have the moderate opportunity and 37% feel that they have significant opportunity to get around.

In this era of extreme competition health of an individual is extremely compromised, this competition is due to the conditions arise in the medical profession .Thus , bringing stress to their life affect their quality of life. Medicine being a significant tough profession has an impact, not only on the physical and physiological health of individuals but also on the social and environmental behavior. Various studies have been done in the past to confirm this association. One of the studies shows that the negative effects and feelings of depression increase with increasing studying class[4] whereas according to our study 44% of the students never have such feeling while 35 % seldom have such feelings. According to another study frequency of symptoms of depression increase in direct proportion to the duration of time spent in this profession. High profession ,prolonged stress, and perfectionist personalities predispose medical practitioners to mental illness wrote a 3rd-year medical student from UNSW. In another study, The earned score of students in the social domain was at least 6.4 and at most 20 (mean= 13.7 and SE= 0.20).

The score of students in the environmental domain was between 5.5 and at most 20 (mean= 13.1 and SE= 0.16). No significant difference was seen between the female and male students in terms of environmental health level,

The students' QOL are good in two environmental and psychological health and poor in physical health and social relationships. As the educational level goes up in all four domains, the QOL decreases and internship level found to be of a crucial position as the QOL in that stage reaches to its lowest level [5] whereas in our

study, majority students have good quality of life with respect to social domain and have a satisfactory quality of life with respect to environmental domain, and an overall good quality of life

Conclusion:

The objective of study has been achieved to a great extent. The major result includes the fact that majority of the medical students have a good Quality of life. A small number of them have a very good Quality of life, while a negligible number of them have a poor or very poor quality of life. Students are especially more satisfied with their physical health when compared with other domains. Majority of them rarely have feelings of anxiety, depression, and despair. Various limitations in the pathway of study include limited time; moreover, the field of data collection was narrowed to keep the questionnaire short. Further studies should be done to compare the medical students' quality of life with the general population or with the students of other professions.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

Physical activity is beneficial to the students, especially in their academic performance. Thus, medical college authorities should recognize the positive aspects of physical activity on students and encourage them to participate in various extra-curricular activities. But these activities should be at a moderate level and not at the expense of their studies.

1. Improve awareness of and access to non-gym-based physical activity opportunities. Living an active lifestyle by integrating physical activity into an individual's daily routine can be an effective way to increase personal fitness.
2. The use of peer support and interactive social groups, such as classes and clubs, can increase engagement in physical activity by giving students the opportunity to be connected to other students and staff members, thereby enabling them to monitor their progress and encouraging them to continue their activities.
3. Encourage community design and development that increase the capacity for walking, bicycling, and other self-powered transportation.

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